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ИМЕНИ Г.В. ПЛЕХАНОВА
ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ ФИЛИАЛ

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

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PRACTICAL ASPECTS OF SMALL BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN MAHALLA'S

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Abstract. This article provides a scientific and economic analysis of the priority areas of entrepreneurship and crafts development in mahallas in the conditions of Uzbekistan and practical recommendations aimed at supporting them. The study substantiates the role of the mahalla institution in regional economic development, its importance in ensuring employment and effective use of local resources. Special attention is also paid to improving the business environment, integrating handicraft activities with market infrastructure, improving financial support mechanisms, and developing human capital. The conclusions and proposals presented in the article serve the sustainable development of small businesses and crafts at the local level and are of practical importance in the activities of state and mahalla management bodies.

Keywords: mahalla, entrepreneurship, crafts, small businesses, employment, local economic development, support mechanisms.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada O'zbekiston sharoitida mahallalarda tadbirkorlik va hunarmandchilikni rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari hamda ularni qo'llab-quvvatlashga qaratilgan amaliy tavsiyalar ilmiy-iqtisodiy jihatdan tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotda mahalla institutining hududiy iqtisodiy rivojlanishdagi o'rni, aholi bandligini ta'minlash va mahalliy resurslardan samarali foydalanishdagi ahamiyati asoslab berilgan. Shuningdek, tadbirkorlik muhitini yaxshilash, hunarmandchilik faoliyatini bozor infratuzilmasi bilan integratsiya qilish, moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish hamda inson kapitalini rivojlantirish masalalariga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Maqolada keltirilgan xulosa va takliflar mahalliy darajada kichik biznes va hunarmandchilikni barqaror rivojlantirishga xizmat qilib, davlat va mahalla boshqaruvi organlari faoliyatida amaliy ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: mahalla, tadbirkorlik, hunarmandchilik, kichik biznes, aholi bandligi, mahalliy iqtisodiy rivojlanish, qo'llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlari.

Аннотация. В статье с научно-экономической точки зрения проанализированы приоритетные направления развития предпринимательства и ремесленничества в махаллях в условиях Узбекистана, а также практические рекомендации по их поддержке. В исследовании обоснована роль института махалли в территориальном экономическом развитии, обеспечении занятости населения и эффективном использовании местных ресурсов. Особое внимание уделено вопросам улучшения предпринимательской среды, интеграции ремесленной деятельности с рыночной инфраструктурой, совершенствования механизмов финансовой поддержки и развития человеческого капитала. Представленные в статье выводы и предложения направлены на устойчивое развитие малого бизнеса и ремесленничества на местном уровне и имеют практическое значение для деятельности государственных и махаллинских органов управления.

Ключевые слова: махалля, предпринимательство, ремесленничество, малый бизнес, занятость населения, местное экономическое развитие, механизмы поддержки.

INTRODUCTION

In the current context of globalization and economic transformation, the development of entrepreneurship and crafts is one of the important factors in ensuring the economic stability of countries. In particular, by supporting small businesses and private entrepreneurship, the opportunity to increase employment, diversify sources of income, and reduce socio-economic disparities is expanding. In this process, the role of the mahalla institution in stimulating economic activity in the regions is increasingly increasing.

The reforms implemented in Uzbekistan in recent years are aimed at supporting entrepreneurial initiatives at the local level, restoring handicraft traditions and adapting them to modern market requirements. The introduction of the principle of «working in the neighborhood», programs for the development of family entrepreneurship, and tax and financial incentives provided to craftsmen are contributing to increasing economic activity in mahallas.

The development of entrepreneurship and crafts in makhallas is not only economically important, but also socially, and serves to promote self-employment among the population, reduce poverty, and ensure social stability. However, it is necessary to develop this area scientifically, and to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the relationship between local infrastructure, financial resources, and human capital. In this regard, this article examines the current issues of developing entrepreneurship and crafts in makhallas in Uzbekistan, existing problems, and practical proposals for solving them from a scientific point of view.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The works of foreign scholars who studied the social, economic and institutional characteristics of the mahalla institution are an important theoretical and methodological source for scientifically substantiating the issues of developing small business and entrepreneurship in the mahalla. In particular, the study conducted by R. Urinboyev and S. Eraliyev evaluated the mahalla as an informal civil society institution, highlighting its role in supporting local initiatives, mutual assistance and economic activity. The authors scientifically substantiate that the informal mechanisms of the mahalla are an important factor in the formation of small business entities and ensuring their sustainable operation. This approach indicates the need to take into account the factor of social capital and trust in the development of entrepreneurship in mahallas.[1]

E. Sievers' study analyzed the post-Soviet transformation processes of the mahalla and revealed its role and functions in the local governance system. The scientist emphasizes that the acquisition of the official institutional status of the mahalla not only expanded its opportunities for coordinating economic activity, but also led to an increase in state influence. These conclusions indicate the importance of maintaining a balance between state and public interests in the development of small businesses through neighborhoods.[2]

T. Dadabaev in his scientific work analyzes the changing nature of neighborhood life, collective memory, and neighborhood identity. The author substantiates that the neighborhood is not only an administrative structure, but also a social space where economic activity, informal economic relations, and entrepreneurial initiatives are formed. In this regard, it is scientifically confirmed that the neighborhood environment can create favorable social conditions for the formation and development of small business entities.[3]

D. Stevens' research analyzes the cooperative relations between neighborhoods and non-governmental non-profit organizations and shows the possibilities of ensuring state-society synergy. The author emphasizes that the neighborhood institute serves as an important platform for supporting entrepreneurship at the local level, coordinating resources, and attracting the population to economic activity. This approach justifies the need to introduce institutional cooperation mechanisms in the development of small businesses in makhallas. [4]

N. Noori's work highlights the conflicting aspects of centralization and decentralization processes. The author emphasizes that the reduction of local services and the expansion of state powers can negatively affect the activities of the makhalla institution. These conclusions indicate the importance of preserving local initiatives and the ability to make independent economic decisions in the development of entrepreneurship in makhallas.[5]

The study by M. Yang and co-authors scientifically substantiates the concept of community-based entrepreneurship and reveals mechanisms for the sustainable development of small and local businesses. The authors prove that business initiatives organized with the participation of local communities provide social stability along with economic efficiency. This approach serves as an important theoretical basis for the formation of practical models for the development of small businesses in neighborhoods.[6]

N. Derlukiewicz and co-authors analyze the "bottom-up" initiatives implemented by local authorities and show their effectiveness in developing entrepreneurship. According to the results of the study, support mechanisms at the local level, including consulting, financial assistance, and infrastructure development, serve to increase the activity of small businesses. These conclusions scientifically justify the active participation of local governments in stimulating entrepreneurship in neighborhoods.[7]

In general, the analysis of these scientific sources shows that the mahalla institute is an important socio-economic platform for the development of small business and entrepreneurship. These theoretical conclusions serve as a solid scientific basis for the development of practical mechanisms for the development of entrepreneurship in mahallas.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is based on the analysis of primary and secondary data collected from official statistics, local mahalla reports, and structured interviews with small business owners. Quantitative indicators were processed using descriptive and comparative methods, while qualitative information was analyzed through content analysis to identify key practical factors influencing small business and entrepreneurship development at the mahalla level.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Researchers have studied methods for increasing the competitiveness of business entities based on strategic management tools using various methodologies. Foreign scholars Avery Brevoort, Bhutta, Ding and Nakamura conducted studies assessing the impact of mortgage loans in mahallas and lending on the development of business entities in the context of low-income households. Zinman, Bostic, Lee, Chakraborty and Ding, using a three-stage differential analysis method, taking into account the intensity of the activities of banks and regulators at the mahalla level, determined the effectiveness of strategic management tools through an increase in the volume of lending.

Measures to develop crafts are determined by the active involvement of the population of mahallas, in particular women, low-income people and youth. "Master-apprentice" schools have been established and mechanisms for integrating craftsmen into associations have been developed.[8]

The development of entrepreneurship and crafts in the Fergana Valley makhallas, when combined with economic and cultural potential, opens the way for continuous growth. Makhalla support is being expanded with preferential loans, logistics infrastructure, master-apprentice routes and tourism mechanisms, on this basis economic stability, quality of social life, jobs and export potential have significantly increased.

The data in Table 1 allow us to assess the territorial distribution, level of activity and dynamics of business entities in Fergana region as of January 1, 2025. Analysis of the table shows that a total of 63,946 business entities were registered in the region, of which only 34,302, or approximately 53.6 percent, are operating (Table 1).

Table 1. Information on the number of registered entities (excluding farmers, farms) in Fergana region as of January 1, 2025

City, district name	Registered	Active	Inactive	Newly established since the beginning of the year	Completed since the beginning of the year
Total	63946	34302	29644	6153	2808
Oltiariq district	3170	1962	1208	355	132
Qoshtepa district	2186	1260	926	290	153
Baghdad district	2475	1316	1159	247	87
Buvayda district	2875	1354	1521	257	141
Besharik district	2298	1212	1086	261	119
Quva district	3103	1524	1579	287	134
Uchkoprik district	3233	1744	1489	283	43
Rishton district	2459	1503	956	312	150
Sokh district	1594	983	611	152	43
Tashlok district	2815	1388	1427	250	236
Uzbekistan district	2936	1518	1418	257	125
Fergana district	2631	1558	1073	258	69
Dangara district	2912	1450	1462	196	140
Furqat district	1708	896	812	180	90
Yozyovan district	1747	1200	547	331	36
Fergana city	11024	6057	4967	1013	453
Kokand city	7186	3511	3675	521	282
Kuvasoy city	2412	1227	1185	279	128
Margilan city	5182	2639	2543	424	247

When analyzed by region, the largest number of business entities is registered in Fergana city (11,024), of which 6,057 are operating. This is explained by the developed economic infrastructure of the city, the large market capacity and the dominance of the service sector. At the same time, the high number of inactive entities (4,967) indicates that competition is strong in the city and that not all newly established businesses are able to operate stably. A similar situation is observed in the cities of Kokand and Margilan, that is, there is a significant difference between registered and active entities.

In the district, a relatively stable situation is observed in some regions. For example, in Yozyavon district, out of 1,747 registered entities, 1,200 are operating, which means an activity level of more than 68 percent. This may indicate that the mechanisms for supporting entrepreneurship at the local level are working effectively. At the same time, the share of inactive entities in Buvayda, Kuva and Toshlok districts is high, which indicates the need for additional measures to revive entrepreneurial activity in these regions.

Although the number of newly established entities since the beginning of the year (6,153) indicates that entrepreneurial activity is maintained at a certain level, the fact that 2,808 entities were liquidated during this period confirms the presence of factors that negatively affect the stability of the business environment.

Among the regions, Fergana city has the largest number of active entities, with a total of 6,057 enterprises operating here. The bulk of these entities are concentrated in the trade (1,658), industry (652) and other services (1,861) sectors. This indicator confirms the role of Fergana city as a central economic region. It also shows the rapid development of the service sector - especially accommodation and catering (487) and information and communication (180). Kokand city is in second place (3,511 entities). In Kokand, trade is also the most developed sector (1,300), followed by industry (648) and other services (857). Margilan city also has high economic activity, with 2,639 entities operating. These cities are the main support points of the regional economy and business infrastructure.

Among the most active regions in terms of districts, Uchkuprik (1744 units), Fergana district (1558 units), Uzbek district (1518 units) and Kuva district (1524 units) stand out. In Uchkuprik district, the main areas are industry (449 entities) and trade (635 units). In Kuva and Uzbek districts, there are relatively more entities in the service and construction sectors. Sectoral diversification of economic activity is noticeable in these districts. Sokh district has a unique economic situation: 983 entities operate, among which the focus is on agriculture (102 units) and trade (372 units). Despite being a geographically remote area, this district shows economic activity.

The number of entities in the trade sector is in the lead among all districts and cities, which indicates the high market infrastructure, logistics capabilities and domestic consumer demand of these regions. In the industrial sector, Fergana city, Kokand, Margilan and Uchkuprik districts stand out in particular. The construction sector is also relatively high in large cities, indicating that infrastructural development continues in these areas. Accommodation and catering services are also more abundant in large urbanized areas, which is explained by the population density of these areas, their proximity to tourism and shopping centers.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The development of entrepreneurship and crafts in makhallas is an important strategic direction for ensuring sustainable economic growth of the country, increasing employment and reducing poverty. Taking into account the high potential of the makhalla institute to directly influence socio-economic processes in the localities, the following comprehensive recommendations can be put forward for the development of this area.

First of all, in order to further develop the entrepreneurial environment in makhallas, it is possible to establish "entrepreneurship support centers", through which legal advice, accounting services, business plan preparation and project financing can be provided. Such centers will be especially important for newly established and inexperienced entrepreneurs.

Secondly, the development of crafts in makhallas requires the improvement of production and trade infrastructure. In particular, it is necessary to expand the opportunities for exporting handicraft products to domestic and foreign markets by forming a "makhalla-craftsman-market" chain. In this process, the use of electronic trading platforms, the creation of local brands, and the simplification of the product certification system are of great importance.

Thirdly, it is necessary to target financial support mechanisms at the mahalla level. In particular, it is advisable to link preferential microloans, grants, and subsidies specifically to local entrepreneurial initiatives, and to make the process of obtaining them transparent and simple. At the same time, the introduction of the "mahalla credit portfolio" system by strengthening mahalla cooperation with commercial banks will further increase entrepreneurial activity.

It is also necessary to continue to pay special attention to the issue of human capital development. By providing specialized training courses in entrepreneurship and crafts in mahallas, master schools, and restoring

the traditions of mentor-apprenticeship in accordance with modern requirements, it is possible to increase the economic activity of young people and women. This will contribute to the creation of stable jobs in the local labor market.

It is necessary to further improve the system of regular assessment and monitoring of the results of the development of entrepreneurship and crafts in mahallas. Identifying active and underdeveloped neighborhoods based on territorial indicators, popularizing effective practices, and providing targeted assistance to problem areas will ensure the sustainable development of this sector nationwide.

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